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Updated Data Management Plan

WP7: Management

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Executive Summary

Data management is a critical component of research and innovation projects. It involves handling data, preserving it, and making it accessible to other researchers. This updated Data Management Plan (DMP) highlights the datasets produced as part of the project activities that are relevant for inclusion in the DMP. It outlines the types of data generated or gathered during the project, the standards applied, the methods for exploiting and sharing data for verification or reuse, and the strategies for data preservation.

The DMP is a living document that evolves throughout the project's lifecycle, particularly when significant changes occur, such as dataset updates or modifications to Consortium policies. This updated version of the DMP builds on the foundational document delivered in Month 6 of the project. It provides an overview of the datasets produced by the project and outlines the specific conditions attached to them. While this version continues to cover a wide range of aspects related to Plasma-PEPSC data management, it expands on previous iterations by addressing key areas such as data interoperability and the practical data management procedures implemented by the Plasma-PEPSC project consortium.

This document has been developed in accordance with established guidelines and serves as a consolidated plan for Plasma-PEPSC partners, ensuring adherence to the project's DMP policy.

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1 Introduction

The purpose of the Data Management Plan (DMP) deliverable is to provide relevant information concerning the data that will be collected and used by the partners of the Plasma-PEPSC project.

The DMP describes the data management life cycle for all datasets to be collected, processed, and/or generated by the research project. It covers:

- How data should be handled during and after the project.
- What types and formats of data will be generated/collected.
- Which methodologies and standards will be applied.
- Whether the data be shared or made open-access, and how.
- How data will be curated and preserved during the project as well as after its conclusion.

As with the initial version, this updated Data Management Plan (DMP) provides preliminary information about the data generated by the project, including whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, as well as how it will be curated and preserved. The purpose of this DMP is to analyze the main elements of the data management policy that the consortium will follow for all datasets generated during the project.

In this updated version, several significant changes have been made compared to the previous version. These include updates to the potential data formats, revisions to the Plasma-PEPSC Code Licenses and Repositories, now featuring mirrored releases to Castiel 2, and the addition of a new section on Research Data Outcomes and Impact. The document has been thoroughly reviewed and expanded to provide more detailed information, ensuring a comprehensive approach to data management.

The DMP is a living document that will evolve throughout the project's lifespan. It will be updated as needed to reflect significant changes, such as the introduction of new datasets, modifications to consortium policies, or changes in the consortium's composition.

The remaining part of the document is organized as follows:

- Section 2 describes the updated general principles used to organize project data.
- Section 3 describes the updated data repositories used throughout the project and the management of intellectual properties.
- Section 4 describes the updated research data output plan for the project.
- Section 5 describes the updated research data outcomes and impact.
- Section 6 concludes the deliverable.

2 General Principles Update

This section describes the main aspects to be considered in Plasma-PEPSC’s data management that all partners of the project must follow. In general terms, Plasma-PEPSC’s research data should be “FAIR”, which is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

2.1 FAIR Research Data Management

Plasma-PEPSC will produce two types of data generated by the BIT, GENE, PIconGPU, and Vlasiator plasma codes:

- **Raw data** produced by the simulations as well as performance data from the simulation runs. The former consists of plasma quantities defined on a computational grid (densities, fluid velocities, pressure, temperature, ...) and information about particles or phase-space density (positions, velocities). This raw data will only be used for correctness checking as it can easily be reproduced by rerunning the simulations.
- **Performance data** will consist of execution logs (trace files) as well as profile data, such as hardware performance counter samples. This performance data is the basis for analysis that will be based on a variety of tools and methods. The data generated with the help of these tools will be homogenized in the form of written performance reports that will be made public. These reports will always include artifacts that enable the reproducibility of the results, such as the software build setup, the input parameters, the execution parameters of the simulation, the result correctness check data, and the recorded performance data. The artifact will also point to the exact version (release or git-hash). In very few cases, it is expected to also store a reduced set of the simulation raw data as primary data, e.g., for post-mortem visualizations.

Plasma-PEPSC will investigate the establishment of different systems for data handling, as well as for accessing performance data, analysis, and white papers generated by the project. As already mentioned before, the data will respect the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable). In particular, the project will investigate the use of openPMD¹, a FAIR particle and mesh data format for plasma simulations, developed initially at HZDR, one of its core maintainers to date, to store the direct simulation output.

2.2 Data sources

There are three major sources of data in the frame of the project, as shown below.

- **Simulation Data (SD)**: SD including input, output, and performance data serves as one of the primary sources of data for the project.
- **Source Code for Simulations (SCS)**: SCS for all codes acts as a crucial data source in the project.

¹<https://github.com/openPMD>

- **Documented Output Data (DOD):** DOD such as deliverables, publications, manuals, reports, and more also contribute valuable data to the project.

2.3 Primary research data generated by the project

The project's primary research data will be coming from performance figures, figures supporting software engineering metrics, and other results used to support the research publications produced during the project lifespan. The research is expected to yield results in terms of, e.g., parallel performance (execution time and speedup), reduction in errors, improved time to solution, and improved maintainability.

Full consideration will be given to allowing proper statistical analysis of the results using means, standard deviations, regression tests, and other relevant metrics. Performance data and software engineering results will be derived from parallel source programs. When legally and contractually possible, these sources will also be made public.

Raw data resulting from research is data that has not been coded, grouped, refined, or modified in any way. Even if raw data has more potential use than modified data, as a general rule, the Plasma-PEPSC project will not provide raw data in open repositories due to data quality checking and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) controls. Instead, each partner should keep their sets of raw data, which should be maintained untouched, if possible.

2.4 Confidentiality and data protection concerns

Most of the data described above will be non-confidential, not refer to human subjects, and not introduce any security concerns to increase dissemination and data re-use. However, all research data will be collected and stored in line with European legislation on data protection, as relevant.

For software and data, open-source licenses are promoted in the project. While some partners could retain part of the results with other licenses, this will not be the norm. This rule is explained in the project's Consortium Agreement. Thus, data will be licensed to permit the most extensive re-use possible as soon as possible in the project timeline. Embargoes are not foreseen for software and data.

All data will remain available after the end of the project in open data portals assuming that no budget is needed to keep this data open and reusable.

2.5 Preferred data formats

Data will generally be stored as plain text to simplify processing and avoid possible problems with transcribing data between evolving data formats.

For research data exchange, CSV (Comma-separated Values) format is preferred. However, each dataset stored in the repository will include a description of the data. Templates are provided for documents and other dissemination data of the Plasma-PEPSC project. Those templates are mandatory to enhance compatibility and inspection inside the project.

All data elements must incorporate attribution of their original source, date, and authors. If several contributions are made over time, a change log is required.

Table 1 shows the preferred formats and those accepted in the Plasma-PEPSC data catalog. Preferred formats have been chosen because they are suggested to have the highest probability of maintaining accessibility and readability in the future. Accepted formats are commonly used formats that have good prospects of remaining readable in the long term.

Document type	Preferred format	Accepted format
Text documents	plain (.txt)	MS Word
	PDF	Rich Text Format
	TeX	
Markup language	JSON	XML
		XML
Spreadsheets	CSV	MS Excel (.xls)
		OpenDocument Spreadsheet
Images	PNG	TIFF
	SVG	JPEG, PDF
Databases	CSV	SQL
	JSON	OpenDocument Base
Simulation Outputs	ADIOS2, HDF5, JSON	ASCII
	VLSV	NetCDF

Table 1: Potential data formats in Plasma-PEPSC

2.6 Tools for validating results

Complete information will be provided in the research publications about the tools that have been used to produce the results, including details of operating system versions, libraries, and specific software tools, as relevant.

Most of the software tools that will be used in the project will be free, open-source software, either produced by third parties or produced by the project and disseminated under open licenses. Full care will, however, be taken to avoid releasing proprietary software and to achieve the best possible commercial exploitation for tools that are developed and/or modified during the project.

Where tools are restricted, it will generally be possible to obtain them under some sufficiently liberal license agreement to allow full reproduction of the research experiments.

2.7 Source code

Plasma-PEPSC's source code(s) will be developed using the coding standard defined in the project. This coding standard is not mandatory for already-established projects that are already using their own coding standard that could keep on using the existing coding standard.

2.8 Data security

All research data underpinning publications will be made available for verification and re-use unless there are justified reasons for keeping specific datasets confidential. The main elements when considering the confidentiality of datasets are:

- Protection of intellectual property regarding new processes, products, and technologies where the data could be used to derive sensitive information that would impact the competitive advantage of the consortium or its members,
- Commercial agreements as part of the procurement of components or materials that might foresee the confidentiality of data.
- Personal data that might have been collected in the project where sharing them is not allowed by national and European legislation.

2.9 Data quality

Data quality control will be part of the project's quality management plan. Inaccurate data is challenging to detect, but some procedures to check them have been put in place in the Plasma-PEPSC project to remove as many errors as possible before data publication:

- Double review of deliverables.
- Quality supervision at the work package level of the data produced in each work package.
- Peer review of documents, software, and papers.
- Comparison of new outputs with previous results to ensure consistency.
- Regular testing by teams to verify that new results align with expectations.
- Automated scripts to detect unusual or potentially erroneous results.

Documentation and deliverables will be hierarchically organized via a knowledge base whose elements will be readable by all project partners. Write access, administration, and use of quality-control tools will be available for those responsible.

As project coordinator, KTH will ultimately be responsible for data quality control and coordinating the data quality plan. However, the data quality control will be organized hierarchically in a bottom-up process:

- Data producers will primarily ensure data quality and conformance with the required standards.
- Peer reviewers will oversee data quality reviews and be co-responsible for potential issues not reported.
- Work package leaders will be responsible for controlling the data quality of the data produced in their WPs.
- Scientific Coordinator will be the next control level for data produced as a result of the research.
- The project coordinator and the project manager will be ultimately responsible for the data quality control and coordinating the data quality plan.

2.10 Allocation of resources

Resources for the data management plan (DMP) are mostly allocated to Project Management in the work package (WP7) and Project Dissemination and Exploitation in the work package (WP6).

2.11 Ethics

The Plasma-PEPSC project does not foresee handling data with any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing.

3 Data Repositories and Management of Intellectual Properties Update

This section describes the repositories to be used in the Plasma-PEPSC project for public and private data management and management of intellectual properties.

3.1 Public repositories

The Plasma-PEPSC project will publish performance data mainly in open-access repositories to increase the project's impact and promote results exploitation. Open-access repositories, such as institutional repositories or disciplinary repositories, provide free access to research for users outside the institutional community.

For storing, preserving, and sharing data, Plasma-PEPSC will rely on standard repositories that will provide services for managing data in a secure and persistent manner.

For software development, we will set up internal repositories (e.g., GitLab), while for software distribution, we will rely on the GitLab of the project and standard repositories such as GitHub and Bitbucket. All repositories for the Plasma-PEPSC project, including those for BIT, GENE, GENEX, PICongGPU, and Vlasiator, are mirrored to Castiel 2, with license details and access links provided in Table 2.

Plasma Code	Licence	Repositories
BIT	Free Customised Licence (Request to IPP CAS)	https://repo.tok.ipp.cas.cz/tskhakaya/bit1
BIT	Mirrored Release	https://codehub.hlrs.de/coes/plasma-pepsc/ippcas/bit1
GENE	Free Customised licence (request to MPG)	https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/GENE/gene
GENE	Mirrored Release	https://codehub.hlrs.de/coes/plasma-pepsc/mpg/gene
GENEX	New Release	https://gitlab.mpcdf.mpg.de/phoenix-public/genex
PICongGPU	GPLv3+	https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/picongpu
PICongGPU	Mirrored Release	https://codehub.hlrs.de/coes/plasma-pepsc/hzdr/picongpu
Vlasiator	GPL2	https://github.com/fmihpc/vlasiator
Vlasiator	Mirrored Release	https://codehub.hlrs.de/coes/plasma-pepsc/uoh/vlasiator

Table 2: Plasma-PEPSC Code Licenses and Repositories

3.2 Consortium private repository

The project consortium employs a private repository for storing all the information necessary to conduct the project. This includes deliverables, journal and conference publications, internal presentations, and media.

Basecamp² repositories (for the whole project and each WP) are set up for hosting project documents and essential management tools. Basecamp also provides functionalities corresponding to mailing lists, and they are being used to keep members informed.

As the project coordinator institution, KTH can manage individual and team access to the organization’s repositories. All members of the project were granted access to the private repository at the beginning of the project. New requests are granted on-demand to the project coordinator.

3.3 Management of Intellectual Properties

All results produced by the partners will belong to their respective developers and their institutions.

All partners will grant access to their IP background and the results to the consortium under the guidelines of a Grant Agreement (GA) that will be signed at the start of the project.

Library / Tool	Use	Licence	Repository
Alpaka	C++17 abstraction library for accelerator development.	MPL-2.0 Licence	https://github.com/alpaka-group/alpaka
Cupla	Conversion library for CUDA applications to Alpaka.	LGPL-3.0	https://github.com/alpaka-group/cupla
Analysator	Python visualisation and post-processing.	GPL-2.0 Licence	https://github.com/fmihpc/analysator
openPMD	I/O, checkpointing, streaming, large scale and in situ data analytics.	LGPL-3.0 Licence	https://github.com/openPMD
FSgrid	Lightweight Cartesian grid library for EM fields.	GNU GPLv3	https://github.com/fmihpc/fsgrid
VLSV	I/O, checkpointing, metadata.	LGPL-3.0 Licence	https://github.com/fmihpc/vlsv
LLAMA	Optimum data representation in heterogeneous memory structures.	LGPL-3.0	https://github.com/alpaka-group/llama
MallocMC	Cross-platform fast memory allocation and management for heterogeneous systems.	MIT	https://github.com/alpaka-group/mallocMC
Bactria	Cross-platform code annotation for performance profiling in heterogeneous systems.	EUPL-1.2	https://github.com/alpaka-group/bactria
RedGrapes	Cross-platform data-dependency aware task creation and scheduling for heterogeneous systems.	MPL-2.0	https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/redGrapes
ISAAC	Cross-platform strongly-coupled in-situ visualisation of particle and cell data with interactive steering for heterogeneous systems.	LGPL-3.0	https://github.com/ComputationalRadiationPhysics/isaac

Table 3: Plasma-PEPSC Code Libraries, Licenses and Repositories

The scientific and technical publications and the software tools developed during the project will be offered in open access unless an explicit mention in the GA prohibits its distribution from protecting IP. The licenses and repository of the four codes are reported in Table 2.

²<https://3.basecamp.com/4072478/projects/26466494>

In addition to the four flagship plasma codes, several libraries will be further developed and used in Plasma-PEPSC to support porting, optimization, and extreme-scale data analysis.

Table 3 summarizes the licenses and open-source repositories used in the project.

4 Research Data Outputs Update

Research data outputs aim to communicate, disseminate, and share the findings and insights derived from research data with the scientific community, policymakers, practitioners, and the public in the European Union (EU).

Table 4 shows our updated data research output plan for Plasma-PEPSC.

Types of data/ research outputs	Findability of data/ research outputs	Accessibility of data/ research outputs	Interoperability of data/ research outputs	Reusability of data research outputs	Costs and responsible team
Performance, Scaling Data	Open-Access reports and white papers	Immediate	Pdf files, trace files, text files with configuration data and tabular outputs	Documents available for analysis and reproducibility studies	No Cost / All consortium
Data generated by Plasma-PEPSC codes Size: Several GB, TB	Plasma-PEPSC data infrastructure (e.g., rodare.hzdr.de)	Immediate accessibility for publication or after an embargo period	Binary, HDF5, DMP, VLSV files, openPMD	Data available for analysis of external data and validation / interpretation / re-use	No cost / IPP CAS, MPG, HDZR, UoH
Simulation codes and software tools for analysis	GitHub / GitLab / BitBucket	Plasma-PEPSC source codes will be made available under different licensing schemes	C, C++, Fortran, Python, IDL source codes	Codes available for analysis of external data and validation / interpretation / re-use	No cost / IPP-CAS, MPG, HDZR, UoH

Table 4: Plasma-PEPSC Research Output Plan

5 Research Data Outcomes and Impact Update

Research data from the project will deliver methods for optimizing plasma simulations and tools for exascale simulations, targeting researchers in computational plasma physics, HPC experts, and fusion energy developers. Key actors include academic institutions, research centers, and industrial partners in HPC and fusion energy across the EU.

Table 5 shows the updated key data related results of the project, the type of outcomes, the targeted community, and a list of specific actors who have the potential to exploit our results.

Key Data Related Results	Type	Community	Target
Four optimised plasma simulation codes efficiently exploiting supercomputers for plasma solving grand challenges, ready to be deployed on large-scale heterogeneous systems	Software	Research	Scientific community, Plasma technologies industry, HPC centres
Performance data from the code analyses (including co-design recommendations) and simulation data from experimental runs	Data	Research	Scientific community, Academia, Plasma technologies industry, HPC centres, HPC technology developers
Software for handling extreme-scale data analytics	Software	Research, Industry	Scientific community, Industry, HPC centres
Reports on porting and optimising plasma simulation codes to new architecture and systems	Report (Publication)	EU, Policy Makers	Industry, Academia HPC centres, HPC technology developers

Table 5: Plasma-PEPSC Research Data Related Results and Targeted Communities

6 Conclusion

The DMP is a cornerstone of research and innovation projects, ensuring the effective handling of data throughout the project lifecycle. It serves as a guiding framework for data generation, curation, sharing, and preservation. As a living document, the DMP is designed to evolve alongside the project, incorporating updates and improvements whenever necessary to reflect new datasets, changes in consortium policies, or advancements in data management practices.

The first version of the DMP, delivered in Month 6 of the project, outlined the types of data expected to be generated or gathered, the standards applied, the methods for exploiting and sharing data for verification or reuse, and the strategies for ensuring long-term preservation. While this initial version established a strong foundation, the updated DMP builds upon it by addressing new opportunities in data management.

This updated version also emphasizes the iterative nature of the DMP. Regular updates will be made as the project progresses, ensuring the plan remains relevant and responsive to the project's evolving needs. By maintaining a dynamic and adaptable DMP, the consortium aims to enhance data management processes, improve collaboration, and ensure the project's outputs are maximized for reuse, reproducibility, and impact.